

Measurement and modeling of solids flow behaviors in an aerated standpipe and inclined pipe of circulating fluidized bed full-loop system

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Tracer accurately measured solids flow in an aerated standpipe and inclined pipe.
- The method can determine the solids flow pattern via selecting a suitable tracer.
- The constructed model can predict solids flow in the presence of aeration gas.
- The model can predict the effect of pressure gradient on the solids flow.
- Effects of pressure gradient can be counteracted by controlling aeration gas flow.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

To control solids circulation and optimize design and operating parameters in a circulating fluidized bed full-loop system, measurement and modeling of solids flow behaviors in an aerated standpipe and inclined pipe were conducted. Different aeration gas flows were injected at the inclined pipe, which was equipped with different orifice sizes of 37 mm, 54 mm and 75 mm, for regulating solids flow rates. The magnetic tracer-tracking method, which only needs to inject one small magnetic tracer for each measurement to follow the main solids flow, was successfully demonstrated for measuring sand particles' real-time discharge rates, with good accuracy and no calibration requirement. A mathematical model was constructed to predict solids discharge rates and investigate the adverse effect of the pressure gradient in the standpipe bed in a full loop fluidized bed system. The optimization of the solids-return and circulation unit could therefore be achieved with the tools developed in this study.

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1. Introduction

Solids circulation rate in circulating fluidized bed systems, which refers to the mass flux of particles circulated in the loop between a standpipe and a riser, is an important parameter for the design and operation of CFB reactors, since it can affect both heat and mass transport and determine the gas-solid contact time and the performance of fluidized bed reactors [1–6]. The capacity of solids circulation highly depends on the standpipe design and the corresponding gas-solid interaction. Therefore, understanding of flow patterns in the standpipe in various conditions is critical. A standpipe is a vertical or inclined tube in which particulate solids flow downward back to the bottom of fluidized bed riser under gravity [7], which is often used to maintain a stable solid flow in a solids recycling system. The particle flow rate is generally regulated by the size of standpipe or the orifice at the bottom of the standpipe and the aeration gas flow in the standpipe [8]. For example, the standpipe is generally connected to a loop-seal in industrial CFB systems to transport and return solids collected at a cyclone to the base of the riser while preventing a direct flow of gas from the high pressure riser to the low-pressure standpipe top [9].

Different fluidization regimes can exist in the solids bed in the standpipe of CFB systems. Leung [10] reported two types of flow patterns in the standpipe: fluidized bed flow (particles in suspension); moving-bed flow (particles moving at the voidage of a packed bed and little relative motion between particles). In general, the solids flow in the standpipe is in the moving packed bed regime, while the transformation from the packed-bed flow to the minimum fluidizing state can occur with changing the inner gas-solid slip velocity and the pressure gradient [11,12]. Yao et al. [11] summarized the statuses of the gas-solid flow in the standpipe. When the bed in the standpipe is in minimum fluidization, the pressure drop increases linearly with the bed height [13], while for a transient packed bed, the pressure drop can be described by Ergun's equation as a function of the gas-solid slip velocity [14,15]. The pressure-drop across the standpipe is dynamically changing to keep the full loop pressure balance once the pressure-drop in one component of the whole loop is changed [12,16]. Martín and Ommen [17] investigated and measured pressure fluctuations in an inclined standpipe of a CFB, which was correlated with the solid flux estimated by measuring the time of powder travel over a fixed distance in the visible standpipe. Two different hydrodynamic regimes at different mass fluxes were identified [17]. At low mass flux rates, the regime is characterized by a low dependency of the pressure drop with the aeration flow and a quasi-linear relationship between the standard deviation of pressure fluctuations and the mass flux, while at high mass flux rates there is a low dependency of the mass flux with the standard deviation [17]. The difference was attributed to different sizes of bubbles in the standpipe since the size of the bubbles affects the solids flux and the pressure fluctuations [16,17], indicating the complexities of solids flow in the presence of gas flow.

The flow characteristics in the standpipe can change significantly in the presence of aeration gas, facilitating the return of solid particles to the riser due to the increase of the pressure gradient, consequently, increasing the solid circulation rate and pressure drop of the riser, decreasing the packed bed height [12,18]. Yukselenturk and Yilmaz [19] investigated the effect of aeration rates on the fluidization regimes in a loop seal for a CFB system to identify stable and unstable operating conditions using computational particle fluid dynamics method. Aeration along the length of the standpipe is necessary to fluidize the solids to prevent an irregular flow or low pressure buildup [20]. However, the solids flow can also be hindered by wall bubbles when the aeration flowrate is too high [20]. With increasing the flow rate of aeration air, the flow rate of downward-moving gas flow entrained by the circulating solid increases at first and then decreases because of the presence of bubbles, indicating a transition to bubbling fluidization when the aeration flow is over the critical value [11]. The consequence of the presence of aeration gas flow also depends on the level of the solids mass

flux in the standpipe [20]. For example, startup tests of the standpipe of a Fluid Catalytic Cracking process (FCC) showed that [20]: at low solids fluxes, the whole standpipe can be fluidized due to rising bubbles by the bottom aeration tap; at intermediate fluxes the solids flow rate cannot evacuate all the injected gas but can be high enough to slow down the upwardly moving bubbles, resulting in a high risk of formation of large bubbles and slug flows that would seriously perturb standpipe operation; when at high solid fluxes, the standpipe nears its capacity, and it is therefore essential to optimize the aeration values to avoid defluidization or large wall jets. An uncontrolled aeration rate might result in the increase of bubble sizes [21], forming a slug flow, which hinders the particles moving downward [12,22]. The flow in the standpipe can become unstable if large gas bubbles are formed since bubbles rising against the downward-flowing solids hinder or limit the solids flow rate [23]. Flow instability can occur when the downward solid flow is not sufficient to hold gas bubbles stationary in the standpipe and the size of escaped bubbles increases and results in a slug flow in the standpipe [24]. Types and sizes of particles also matter. The solids with a small range of non-bubbling fluidization, such as coarse, denser catalysts, are more likely to give rise to bubbles that grow by coalescence when rising against the downward solids flow, hindering the solids flow rate and causing an unstable flow due to the formation of large stable bubbles [23,25,26].

An optimum aeration strategy is therefore critical in controlling the performance of the standpipe. Chong et al. [7] proposed an aeration strategy to achieve a highly-uniform mixture density throughout the standpipe since a low mixture density and high voidage in the standpipe can result in poor pressure build-up and inadequate solids circulation [7]. Shioij et al. [8] investigated the discharge of granular materials through a vertical standpipe with an orifice at the end of the pipe and aeration injection nozzles at the bottom part from a low pressure region to a high pressure region. It is reported that the particle flow against the pressure difference was more stable when in the presence of aeration air. The discharge limit and instability of the particle flow against the imposed pressure difference can be improved by introducing aeration air. There is a strong demand to maintain a dense-phase downflow in the standpipe to maximize solids circulation in certain applications, e.g., Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) Units [27]. Transition from the dense-phase regime to the lean-phase regime would lead to gas back-flow, decreasing the circulation rate and even giving rise to bridging with zero solids flow [28]. For example, the standpipe must operate in the dense-phase regime to provide a pressure seal sufficient to maintain a high catalyst inventory in the reaction zone in a Synthol Circulating Fluidized-Bed (CFB) reactor [28]. Moreover, the operation of standpipe also needs to be flexible to follow the change of the system. Lin et al. [13] injected batches of radioactive tracer particles into the standpipe in an 80 MWth circulating fluidized-bed boiler and reported that there were significant differences in the response signals when the boiler loading changed. The measured mean descending velocity of particles in the dense bed was 0.34 and 0.08 m/s at full- and part- loads, respectively. With decreasing the boiler load, the pressure difference and bed inventory distribution between the loop-seal and furnace changed, consequently influencing the recirculating rate of solids particles [13]. Therefore, the aeration design also needs to be adapted to fulfill the requirements of operation flexibility.

An accurate online measurement that can measure the solids circulation rate and determine the gas-solid behaviors and fluidization behaviors in the standpipe is therefore very important to quantify the effect of operating and design parameters on the performance of circulating fluidized beds. Many measuring technologies have been introduced in the literature to measure solids circulation rate [1,17]. Some methods tried to correlate main operating parameters in a fluidized bed riser, such as pressure drop [5], local momentum flux of gas-solids flow [29–32], concentrations and velocity distributions of the solid particles [33,34], and fluctuation, to the solid flux [17]; however, calibration is still needed and it is hard to establish their general applicability due to

variation in operating conditions and geometries [35]. Moreover, since the local time-average solid mass flux can vary with axial and radial positions, elevation, total solids mass flow, superficial gas velocity, and mean particle diameter [30,31], a detailed picture of the flow structure over the bed's cross-sectional area of the circulating fluidized bed is needed to calculate the total circulation rate by the integral of the product of concentration multiplied by the corresponding velocity in the cross section [36,37]. The most basic and easiest method is to collect and measure particles accumulation from the standpipe [1]. The accumulation method is to suddenly stop particles flowing by regulating a porous slide valve or butterfly valve installed in a standpipe and measure the velocity of bed material accumulated above the valve in the standpipe. However, this method can disturb normal solid circulation in CFB loops and the mass ratio of accumulated bed particles over the bed inventory should be minimized to mitigate the disturbance and avoid affecting the steady operation of systems. Tracers, including fluorescent tracer particles [38,39], radioactive particle [40], have been applied into the gas-solid flow for the circulation rate measurement via determining the tracer's moving velocity. The fluorescent tracer, which can be hidden by other bed materials, is generally limited to a quasi-2D flow section and not suitable for the case in the standpipe [1,41]. Radioactive methods are expensive and could imply potential health risks, therefore demanding extraordinary safety measures [42,43]. Therefore, alternative methods that avoid intrusion and complicated calibration for hydrodynamics measurement in these processes are needed. The magnetic-tracer-tracking method has been used in previous studies on bubbling fluidized beds, yielding quantitative information applicable to the study of fuel mixing in large-scale fluidized bed processes, overcoming the limitation in signal penetration which prevents tracking of radioactive objects in such dense media [44–46]. The method can be used to measure solids moving velocity and determine the fluidization status in an aerated standpipe and inclined pipe. Only a single small magnetic is injected for each measurement test. The tracer's diameter, depending on the size of plastic casing, is typically around several millimeters, much less than the diameters of fluidized bed risers and standpipes. Therefore, the tracer does not affect the solids flow in the system and can be considered as a non-invasive method. The work published in [47] thoroughly investigated the measurement accuracy of solids circulation rates when using the magnetic tracer-tracking method under various conditions, e.g. tracer sizes, orifice sizes in the standpipe, and the presence of an inclined pipe. It reports that the single tracer's velocity in the axial direction can well represent the solids' discharge velocity except the rig configuration with a very narrow orifice and without inclined pipe. However, adverse effects caused by narrow orifice were also addressed by constructing a model to correct velocity distribution in the cross-sectional area. Since the tracer sensing system (magnetic sensor nodes) is installed outside the pressure vessel to track the tracer, this method can also be easily applied for measuring solids circulation in a pressurized fluidized bed system, which is challenging for conventional methods, e.g. accumulation methods, optic probes. The pressurized fluidized bed technology is considered a promising route for energy conversion and carbon capture, to utilize biomass with a high efficiency in combined heat and power production, i.e. integrated gasification combined cycle (IGCC) system, and for production of chemical energy carriers in the chemical industry [48–51]. Moreover, the magnetic tracer-tracking method has a high potential of the circulation measurement in a system at elevated temperatures, via selecting suitable magnetic materials with a high working temperature of the tracers, e.g. NdFeB based magnets (about 250 °C), SmCo based magnets (up to 550 °C) [52–54].

In this study, measurement tests of solids flow using the magnetic tracer-tracking method were first conducted in the presence of aeration gas flows in a pilot-scale solids-return unit that consists of a vertical standpipe and an inclined pipe, which was constructed for solids return in a pressurized fluidized bed gasification process. Compared to the loop seal that has been widely adopted in circulating fluidized bed systems,

the inclined pipe is advantageous due to the high flexibility to follow load and pressure ramping, since the pressure in the system can be balanced quickly when changing the operating parameters. Moreover, it also has a low manufacturing cost due to a simple geometry and a thinner pressure vessel. An orifice was installed at the end of the inclined pipe to regulate the solids flow, with purposes of investigating the effect of the change of the solids passage. The strategy of aeration gas injection in the inclined pipe was examined. A mathematical model was constructed to describe and predict the solids mass flow when using different orifice sizes and different aeration gas flow rates. In a full-loop fluidized bed system, a pressure gradient over the bed in the standpipe always exists due to the relatively high pressure in the riser bottom which is connected to the bottom of the inclined pipe compared to the standpipe top. Therefore, the injected aeration gas, highly depending on the solids bed height and the pressure gradient, could also flow upward partially or fully, which might change the gas-solid flow pattern and hinder the solids discharge in the standpipe. Thus, it is important that the applied measurement tool of the solids flow can also accurately determine the gas-solid flow status and pattern in the standpipe, especially when in the presence of a high flow of aeration gas. Tracers with different sizes and densities were then used and compared, to test their sensitivities in the presence of gas bubbles. Moreover, the constructed mathematical model was further developed to investigate and describe the effect of pressure gradients and aeration gas flow rates on the solids flow in the solids-return unit in a full-loop fluidized bed system, which can improve the control strategies of fluidized bed operation and aeration gas injection and optimize the system design.

2. Methodology

2.1. Experimental apparatus

A pressurized fluidized bed system (RISE, Piteå) was constructed for hydrodynamics tests under pressurized conditions. The system consists of a riser, a cyclone, a standpipe, and an inclined pipe, with the schematic diagram shown in Fig. 1(a). The vertical standpipe was made of Plexiglas pipe and installed in a stainless pressure vessel. The Plexiglas pipe and the inclined pipe have the same inner diameter of 123 mm but different pipe lengths of around 5 and 0.8 m, respectively. The angle of the inclined pipe to the horizontal is 52.5°. There are three aeration nozzles along different heights of the inclined pipe, with the lower one close to the orifice exit and the upper one at the bottom of the vertical standpipe. The fluidization gas in the riser is injected via a distributor. Bed particles in the riser can then be entrained to the riser top with the fluidization gas, collected by the cyclone, and finally returned to the bottom of the riser via the vertical standpipe and inclined pipe, forming a circulation of solid particles in the full-loop fluidized bed system.

In this study, to investigate the particles discharge flow behaviors in the bed-return system, the vertical standpipe and inclined pipe were used, as shown in Fig. 1(b). To regulate the solid flows, orifices with different openings were used at the exit of the inclined pipe. A controlled aeration gas flow, supplied by a compressed air system, can be injected at the lower aeration nozzle close to the exit of the inclined pipe to assist the movement of solids in the standpipe and inclined pipe. A bucket loaded on a weighing scale was used to collect particles discharged from the vertical standpipe and inclined pipe. Two arrays of magnetic sensor nodes with 4 magnetic sensor nodes in each array were installed at different heights surrounding the pressure vessel of the standpipe, denoted by green rectangles in the upper sensing zone, as shown in Fig. 1(b) and (c). The vertical standpipe was also equipped with glass windows at different levels for visual observation of solids movement in the transparent Plexiglas standpipe. The coordinate axes of the measurement sensing zone are illustrated in Fig. 1(d). One more array of magnetic sensor nodes with 4 magnetic sensor nodes was installed in the lower sensing zone surrounding the inclined pipe. The sensor nodes are around 10 cm away from the orifice exit in the length direction of the

Fig. 1. Pressurized fluidized bed system at RISE, Piteå: (a) a full-loop pressurized fluidized bed system with installed magnetic tracer-tracking system, including riser (1), cyclone (2), standpipe (3), inclined pipe (4), glass windows (5), pressure vessel wall (6), plexiglass (7), magnetic tracer upper sensing zone (8), magnetic tracer lower sensing zone (9), transition zone (10), blind plate & orifice (11), lower aeration gas injection nozzle (12), middle aeration gas injection nozzle (13), upper aeration gas injection nozzle (14), recycling container and weighing scale (15); (b) testing system used in this study; (c) installed magnetic sensors in the upper sensing zone surrounding the standpipe; (d) coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system in the upper sensing zone; (e) coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system in the lower sensing zone; (f) schematic image of the magnetic tracer with a magnetic moment, μ_m , located at position x, y, z and oriented with angles θ, φ with respect to the coordinate system.

inclined pipe. The coordinate axes of the lower sensing measurement system are shown in Fig. 1(e). The sensing zone was defined by its detectable area, starting from where the signal appears and finishing where the tracer moves out from the lower detection limit. The zone between the upper sensing and lower sensing zones is denoted as a transition zone.

2.2. Measurement method

2.2.1. Magnetic tracer-tracking system

The magnetic tracer-tracking system consists of a number of magnetic field sensors (magnetic sensor nodes) that read the stray magnetic field in three dimensions from the magnetic tracer element (e.g. NdFeB-based permanent magnet) [44]. The magnetic stray field from the magnetic tracer can be considered as the field from a magnetic dipole with a magnetic moment, μ_m . From the readings of the surrounding magnetic sensor nodes and using optimization fitting algorithms, the time dependent positions, x, y and z , and orientations, θ, φ of the magnetic moment of the tracer can be determined, see Fig. 1(f). The sensor nodes read the magnetic stray field from the magnetic tracer that depends on the position and orientation of the tracer with respect to the sensor node. For clarity in the figure, only one sensor node is shown. In the real system several sensor nodes surrounding the measuring volume were used. The z -axis is in the length direction of the standpipe and

inclined pipe.

One advantage of the magnetic tracer-tracking system is that no clear optical line of sight is needed between the sensors and the magnetic tracer to be measured, as long as the standpipe material is not made of any magnetic material that shields the stray fields from the magnetic tracer or distorts the magnetic fields at the magnetic sensors. Not only can the time evaluation of the tracer position (which gives the flow velocity) be determined, but also the orientation of the tracer. The tracer orientation gives valuable information of the flow in the standpipe. The magnetic tracers are made of a magnetic inner core of NdFeB-based cylindrical magnets symmetrically positioned in a spherical polymer shell (3D-printed) that builds up the tracer element. The polymer shell is made of PETG (Polyethylene Terephthalate with Glycol) and the NdFeB-based magnets are of grade N35 (3 × 3 mm cylinder) with a remanence magnetization of 1.2 T. The effective density of the tracer elements is determined by considering the total tracer mass (sum of magnet and polymer shell) divided by the total tracer volume. The bare magnetic tracer has a much larger diameter and larger particle density than the solids particles in the standpipe. However, by wrapping the tracer using a plastic casing with different sizes, the effective tracer density changes, therefore regulating fluid-dynamic similarity between the tracer and the fluid materials. The bare magnetic tracer has a particle density of 7600 kg/m³. The tracer density can be lowered to around 1000 kg/m³ by using an 8 mm spherical polymer shell, which is similar to the level of

the bulk density of solids particles in the standpipe.

The magnetic reading system consists of several sensor nodes including three-axis magnetometers from Honeywell (HMC 1053) and electronics for signal amplification, analog-to-digital converting and sampling. Also, on each sensor node there are electronics for sending the data to a main control module on a common RS485 bus. The control module communicates by User Datagram Protocol (UDP) to the Ethernet port on a PC that controls the measurement and stores the data. The sampling frequency is 100 Hz. The sensor nodes were mounted on an aluminum frame, which is non-magnetic and has no impact on sensors' measurement. The aluminum frame was fixed on the external wall of the pressure vessel, which is made of a stainless-steel pipe. Since the stainless-steel pipe is non-magnetic and does not distort the magnetic fields from the tracers, it will not affect the measurements and analysis. Further, the distance between the moving tracer and the stainless-steel pipe is far enough so it will not affect the movement of the tracer.

2.2.2. Accumulation method

A weighing scale (full range 120 kg, measurement accuracy ± 30 g) with a digital displayer was used to continuously measure the mass of accumulated bed particles in a bucket. A camera was used to record the mass accumulation readings of the digital displayer. The solids discharge rate in different time periods can therefore be calculated easily to validate the magnetic tracer-tracking method.

2.3. Experimental tests

2.3.1. Materials

2.3.1.1. Feedstock. Silica sand, supplied by SIBELCO, was used as solids materials in the standpipe during the tests. The particle size distribution is shown in Fig. 2. The materials properties are shown in Table 1 below.

2.3.2. Operating conditions and procedures

Table 2 shows the experimental testing cases and operating conditions. Before starting the test, an orifice was directly installed at the end of the standpipe to regulate the solids discharge flow. After blocking the orifice using a blind plate, silica sand was loaded to the Plexiglas standpipe and inclined pipe. A background measurement was first conducted to measure the background magnetic signals without the magnetic tracer, which then was removed from the following tracer measurement signal. The background signals are subtracted from the tracer signal assuming no dependency between tracer signal and background signal. In the vicinity of the measurement zones no magnetic material is present during background measurements and tracer measurements. The tracer was then injected into the bed. The measurement

Fig. 2. Size distribution of used silica sand.

Table 1
Silica sand materials properties.

Material content	wt%
SiO ₂	90.5
Al ₂ O ₃	4.9
α-Fe ₂ O ₃	0.5
K ₂ O	2.0
Na ₂ O	1.2
Physical properties	
Sintering point	1270 °C
Grain shape	Round-angular
Colour	Beige
Bulk density	1610 kg/m ³

of the magnetic tracer-tracking started prior to withdrawing the bottom blind plate for solids discharge. A bucket was used to collect the solids discharged from the standpipe and the accumulated mass was measured continuously using a weighing scale, which was used to validate the magnetic tracer-tracking measurement method. The effect of orifice sizes (37 mm, 54 mm, and 75 mm) on the solids discharge rate was investigated via tests C#1, C#2, and C#3. Test C#1 was repeated to check the repeatability of testing results. An 8 mm spherical tracer with a 3 × 3 mm inner cylindrical magnet core was used for each measurement. Since the tracer was loaded to the bed surface in C#1, C#2, and C#3, the depth of the tracer immersed in the bed was zero. In test C#4, 20 kg extra silica sand was loaded after dropping the tracer, therefore, the tracer was immersed in the bed with a bed depth of approximately 1.3 m. In tests C#5 and C#6, different aeration gas flows of 5 Nm³/h and 20 Nm³/h were injected at the lower aeration gas point, with the purpose for regulating the solids discharge rate. The effect of aeration gas flows of 5 Nm³/h and 25 Nm³/h on the solids discharge was further investigated in tests from C#7 to C#12, with orifice sizes of 54 mm and 75 mm. The tracer trajectory was acquired continuously during the solids discharge in the vertical standpipe and inclined pipe. The times when the tracer disappeared in the upper sensing zone and appeared in the lower sensing zone were obtained for calculating the travel time of the tracer in the transition zone.

Test C#13 and C#14 were conducted to investigate tracers' movement and sensitivity in the presence of fluidization gas and bubbles, with purposes of selecting a proper tracer for monitoring the status of gas-solids flow in the standpipe. Since the bottom of the inclined pipe is connected to the fluidized bed riser base in a full-loop fluidized bed system, as presented in Fig. 1(a), the pressure at the inclined pipe exit might be higher than that at the standpipe top. In tests C#13 and C#14, a bottom blind plate was used to block the exit of the inclined pipe to prevent the aeration gas flowing downward through the inclined pipe exit. Therefore, the injected aeration gas was guided to only flow upward and form gas bubbles in the sand bed in the standpipe. Two different tracers were used. The 8 mm tracer has a very low particle density of around 1000 kg/m³. On the other hand, the 3 × 3 mm cylindrical bare tracer has a density of 7600 kg/m³ but is smaller in size. The light tracer is apt to fluctuate with the gas and bubble flow in the standpipe, while the heavy tracer is expected to stay in the emulsion phase.

2.3.3. Calculation method of tracer velocity

The data sampling frequency is 100 Hz. The moving average velocity (v_{ij}) of the tracer was calculated every 150 ms based on its position levels (Tz_{ij}) in z direction in the upper sensing zone (vertical standpipe) and the lower sensing zone (inclined pipe), as shown in Eq. (1).

$$v_{ij} = \frac{dTz_{ij}}{dt_{ij}} = \frac{Tz_{ij-5} - Tz_{ij+10}}{0.15} \quad (1)$$

dTz_{ij} is the change of particle position (Tz_{ij-5} , Tz_{ij+10}) in i sensing zone (i.e., 1 denotes the upper sensing zone, and 2 denotes the lower sensing zone) between Tz_{ij-5} , sampled at the time index $j-5$, and

Table 2
Experimental tests and operating conditions.

Cases	Test purpose	Orifice size mm	Solids Mass kg	Magnetic tracer depth in the bed m	Magnetic tracer size ^a mm	Aeration gas	
						Aeration flow Nm ³ /h	Aeration point
C#1-1, C#1-2	Discharging	37	46.5	0	8	–	–
C#2	Discharging	54	46.5	0	8	–	–
C#3	Discharging	75	46.5	0	8	–	–
C#4	Discharging	37	66.5	1.3	8	–	–
C#5	Discharging	37	66.5	1.3	8	5	lower
C#6	Discharging	37	66.5	1.3	8	20	lower
C#7	Discharging	54	66.5	1.3	8	–	–
C#8	Discharging	54	66.5	1.3	8	5	lower
C#9	Discharging	54	66.5	1.3	8	25	lower
C#10	Discharging	75	66.5	1.3	8	–	–
C#11	Discharging	75	66.5	1.3	8	5	lower
C#12	Discharging	75	66.5 </td <td>1.3</td> <td>8</td> <td>25</td> <td>lower</td>	1.3	8	25	lower
C#13	Fluidization	Blind plate ^c	66.5	0	8	25	middle ^d
C#14	Fluidization	Blind plate ^c	66.5	0	3.4 ^b	25	upper

^a Outer diameter of the spherical tracer.
^b Volume-equivalent diameter of the cylindrical magnet core.
^c Blind plate was installed at the end of the inclined pipe.
^d 250 mm lower than the upper aeraton nozzle in the vertical direction.

Z_{ij+10} , sampled at the time index $j + 10$. $dt_{i,j}$ is the time zone between the two time points ($j + 10, j - 5$), e.g., 0.15 s in this study since the interval time between two neighboring time indexes is 0.01 s.

The average value of moving average velocities in the upper and lower sensing zones can be calculated.

Fig. 3. Measurement of solids discharge in the upper sensing zone without aeration gas flow in the standpipe: (a) tracer position in z direction in the standpipe with different orifice sizes; (b) effect of orifice size on the mean value of the tracer's moving average velocity; (c) solid discharge rates calculated from both tracer-tracking and accumulation methods; (d) solids movement in xy plane (perpendicular to z axis), the red arrow indicates the direction of the inclined pipe, the standpipe axis is also marked. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$$\bar{v}_{ij} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n v_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of moving average velocities in selected zones.

The corresponding standard deviation σ was calculated, with the expression in Eq. (3).

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (v_{ij} - \bar{v}_{ij})^2} \quad (3)$$

Moreover, the solids moving velocity in the transition zone between the upper and lower sensing zones can also be calculated with the expression in Eq. (4).

$$v_{t,a} = \frac{d_t}{t_{2,b} - t_{1,f}} \quad (4)$$

d_t is the distance between the upper and lower sensing zones. $t_{1,f}$ is the final time of the detected tracer in the upper sensing zone (1 denotes the upper sensing zone, and f denotes the final time index in the upper sensing zone), whereas $t_{2,b}$ represents the initial time of the tracer appearing in the lower sensing zone (2 denotes the lower sensing zone, and b denotes the initial time index in the lower sensing zone).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Measurement of discharge rate in the absence of fluidization gas

3.1.1. Measurement in the vertical standpipe

Fig. 3 shows the measurement of solids discharge in the upper sensing zone without aeration gas in the standpipe. As shown in Fig. 3(a), tracers have an initial position in z direction at around $z = 35$ cm in the coordinate axes of the upper sensing zone and a final position at around $z = 5$ cm before moving out from the upper sensing zone. Tests C#1-1 and C#1-2 were performed with a 37 mm orifice at the exit of the inclined pipe. There is only a slight deviation between the two position profiles in Fig. 3(a). Both tests have a similar travel time of around 11 s in the upper sensing zone and exhibit good repeatability. The travel time in the sensing zone decreases to around 4 and 2 s, when increasing the orifice size to 54 and 75 mm, respectively. The profiles in Fig. 3(a) show good linearity, indicating a steady discharge in the early stage of the whole test. The average value of the moving average velocities in the whole measurement was calculated via Eq. (2), as presented in Fig. 3(b). There is a good linear relationship between the average tracer velocity and the orifice size. Moreover, the standard deviation of the moving average velocities calculated by Eq. (3) is also illustrated together with the average tracer velocity in Fig. 3(b), where the velocity fluctuation of test C#2 and C#3 is around ± 2 cm/s, which is doubled compared to that of test C#1-2 using a 37 mm orifice size. The sand mass flow rates

Fig. 4. Measurement of solids discharge in the lower sensing zone without aeration gas: (a) tracer position in the length direction of the inclined pipe with different orifice sizes; (b) effect of orifice size on the mean value of the moving average velocities; (c) sand discharge rates calculated from both tracer-tracking and accumulation methods; (d) solids movement in xy plane, the red arrow indicates the direction of the inclined pipe, the standpipe axis is also marked. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

calculated by both the magnetic tracer-tracking and accumulation methods were presented and compared in Fig. 3(c). The sand flow calculated by the average tracer velocity in Fig. 3(b) correlates well with that obtained by the accumulation method in the same period. The sand mass flow was also calculated by the velocity obtained by linearly fitting the position profiles in Fig. 3(a), which is almost identical to that calculated by the average tracer velocity. Fig. 3(d) shows the projection of the tracer trajectory in the xy plane, which is marked in different colors based on the elapsed time corresponding to the time in Fig. 3(a). It seems that tracers in tests C#1–1, C#1–2, and C#2 moved toward the direction of the inclined pipe (marked using the arrow in Fig. 3(d)), which indicates the motion of the sand in the standpipe when using the inclined pipe with different orifice sizes.

3.1.2. Measurement in the inclined pipe

After traveling through the upper sensing zone, the tracer continued moving down to the inclined pipe and was detected by sensors in the lower sensing zone, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Since only an array of sensors was used, the sensing zone in the lower sensing zone has a much shorter distance in the length direction of the inclined pipe compared to that of the upper sensing zone. Fig. 4(a) shows the tracer appears at $z = -25$ cm and disappears at $z = -35$ cm in the coordinate axes of the lower sensing zone. All tests in Fig. 4(a) have a travel time of less than 3 s in the sensing zone. The corresponding mean value of the moving average velocities was calculated in Eq. (2) and presented in Fig. 4(b), versus the orifice size. The average tracer velocity increases from around 4 to 11 cm/s with the increase of orifice size from 37 to 54 mm. The increase of the average tracer velocity slows down with a further increase of the orifice size to 75 mm. In test C#1–2, as shown in Fig. 4(c), the calculated sand mass flow based on the average tracer velocity in Fig. 4(b) deviates slightly from that based on the accumulation method in the same period. The deviation is significantly large in test C#2, when increasing the orifice size to 54 mm. In test C#3 with a 75 mm orifice size, the results from both methods fit well with each other. Interesting to note is that the sand mass flow calculated by the accumulation method in the measuring period in the lower sensing zone is almost identical to that calculated for the whole discharge period, as shown in Fig. 4(c), indicating that the bed height in the standpipe and inclined pipe does not have an obvious effect on the sand flow velocity. Fig. 4(d) shows the projection of the tracer trajectory in the xy plane. No tracer experienced much travel in the xy plane due to the short travel time in the lower sensing zone. However, it seems that a trend of tracer's moving toward to the axis center can be observed, as marked by the arrow in Fig. 4(d), indicating the sand particles' motion toward the opening area of used orifice.

3.1.3. Tracer movement in the transition zone

Although the tracer's movement in the transition zone between the upper sensing zone and lower sensing zone was not detected directly, its moving velocity in the transition zone was calculated in Eq. (4) based on the distance and the travel time between the upper and lower sensing zones. As shown in Fig. 4(c), the calculated velocity was used to calculate the sand mass flow in the transition zone, which shows a profile as a function of orifice size like that obtained by the accumulation method, indicating the tracer followed the sand flow in the transition zone. Thus, the method of using the tracer's travel time in the transition zone between the upper and lower sensing zones is validated and can be used to calculate solids' discharge rate.

3.2. Measurement of discharge rate in the presence of aeration gas

As discussed above, the solids discharge is significantly affected by the orifice size, which can be attributed to the change of the stress state of particles in the area at the orifice [55], limiting the solids discharge capacity in the standpipe. However, the stress state of particles can also change when there is a gas flow through the orifice. In this section, the effect of the presence of aeration gas injected from the lower aeration

point of the inclined pipe was investigated, since the aeration gas injected at a position close to the orifice exit might change the gas-solid flow pattern and therefore affect the solids moving-down velocity. Considering that tracers are supposed to be immersed into the bed in the standpipe of a full-loop fluidized bed system due to continuous falling of particles from the cyclone above the standpipe top, the behaviors of tracers immersed in the bed and floated on the bed surface could be different. An in-bed depth of around 1.3 m above the immersed tracer in the standpipe was used in this section.

3.2.1. Tracer velocity in the axial direction

Fig. 5 shows the measurement results of solids discharge in the upper and lower sensing zones with different aeration gas flows and orifice sizes. Tests C#4, C#5, C#6, using a 37 mm orifice but different aeration air flows of 0, 5, and 20 Nm³/h, respectively, have the same initial position in z direction but exhibit different travel times in the upper sensing zone, due to the presence of aeration gas flow, as shown in Fig. 5(a). The travel time decreases from around 10 to 6 s, when increasing the aeration gas flow from 0 to 5 Nm³/h. By further increasing the aeration gas flow to 20 Nm³/h, the travel time decreases to around 3 s. With the aeration gas flow, the decrease of the tracer travel time in the lower sensing zone can also be observed in Fig. 5(a). The effect of aeration gas flow on the travel velocity in the upper and lower sensing zones is shown in Fig. 5(b). The velocity in the vertical standpipe (upper sensing zone) increases from around 3 to 8 cm/s by increasing the aeration flow from 0 to 20 Nm³/h, while with the same aeration flows in the inclined pipe, the increase is much more significant, changing from around 2 to 13 cm/s, indicating a more significant role of the aeration gas in the lower sensing zone when using a narrow orifice at the exit. When increasing the orifice size to 54 cm, the increase of aeration gas flow plays a similar role in decreasing the tracer travel time in the upper and lower sensing zones, as shown in Fig. 5(c). It should be noted that the initial position in z direction of tests C#7, C#8, and C#9 differs, which could be attributed to an uneven bed surface. The corresponding travel velocity is presented in Fig. 5(d), where both profiles exhibit a similar trend of the velocity increase with increasing the aeration gas flow although the velocity in the lower sensing zone is always higher than that in the upper sensing zone. In tests with a 75 mm orifice, as shown in Fig. 5(e), the discharge time of the whole test is significantly lower, compared to that with a 37 mm orifice in Fig. 5(a). The effect of the increase of aeration gas flow on the travel time in the upper and lower sensing zones can still be observed. However, as shown in Fig. 5(f), the effect on the tracer velocity in the lower sensing zone is not as significant as that observed in Fig. 5(b) and (d). Tracer velocity in the inclined pipe with a high aeration gas flow of 25 Nm³/h is even less than that in the vertical standpipe. The aeration gas has a much more significant effect on the tracer velocity in the lower sensing zone when using a narrow orifice since in the lower sensing zone the tracer is close to the lower aeration point, it indicates that a more turbulent field might exist in the area close to the orifice exit and aeration point when injecting a high aeration flow and using a narrow orifice. Some profiles in Fig. 5(c) and 5(e) exhibit a very slow change of position in z direction in the very beginning, indicating the tracer and sands experienced a short acceleration period due to the gravity force. Once the forces exerted on tracer particles reached balance, then the velocity remained relatively constant.

3.2.2. Measurement of solids discharge rate

The sand discharged from the inclined pipe was collected using a bucket and weighed continuously. The mass accumulation curves obtained from the measurement were used to calculate the sand discharge rate. Fig. 6 shows the mass accumulation profiles from tests using a 37 mm orifice at different aeration gas flows. Good linearity can be obtained for test C#4, which has no aeration gas injection and a solids discharge rate of around 0.61 kg/s based on the slope rate of the linear fitting results. The zones corresponding to the tracer movement in the upper and lower sensing zones were marked in Fig. 6, respectively. It is

Fig. 5. Measurement of solids discharge in the upper and lower sensing zones with different aeration gas flows and orifice sizes: (a) tracer position in z direction, orifice size 37 mm; (b) tracer average velocity in z direction, orifice size 37 mm; (c) tracer position in z direction, orifice size 54 mm; (d) tracer average velocity in z direction, orifice size 54 mm; (e) tracer position in z direction, orifice size 75 mm; (f) tracer average velocity in z direction, orifice size 75 mm.

interesting to note that the mass accumulation profiles of tests C#5 and C#6, using 5 and 20 Nm³/h aeration gas, respectively, can be divided into two zones with different slope rates, as separated by the red dash line. As shown in Fig. 6, a linear fitting is obtained until the sand mass accumulation reaches around 62.5 kg, where a turning point can be observed. A linear fitting of the data series after the turning point shows a similar slope rate as that of test C#4, indicating that the effect of aeration gas injection on the solids discharge vanishes after the turning point. The phenomenon can be explained by the change of differential pressures at critical positions in the standpipe, as illustrated in Fig. 7. After withdrawing the blind plate at the exit of the inclined pipe, due to a high initial bed height, if the injected gas went through the bed over the aeration point P_3 , the differential pressure ΔP_{31} between the P_3 and P_1 could be much higher than ΔP_{32} between P_3 and P_2 . Therefore, it is likely that the air injected at the lower aeration point flows out from the orifice exit rather than through the whole bed. However, the flow direction of aeration air flow highly depends on the dynamic change of the

bed height over the aeration point, which decreases with the continuous solids discharge. There should be one critical point where the pressure between the aeration point and the bed top surface equals the differential pressure ΔP_{32} , which is denoted as P_4 , as illustrated in Fig. 7. At P_4 , the differential pressure ΔP_{34} equals ΔP_{32} , therefore, the aeration gas can change flow direction upward through the bed. The position of P_4 might vary when changing the aeration gas flow and the orifice size, since the differential pressure ΔP_{32} also depends on orifice size and the air flow through the orifice.

The distance between P_2 and P_4 can be calculated based on the amount of the sand (m_t) remained in the inclined pipe at P_4 , which can be obtained by subtracting the mass at the turning point from the total mass of loaded sand.

$$l = m_t / (\rho_b A) \quad (5)$$

where ρ_b is the bulk density of the bed in Table 1, A is the cross-sectional area of the inclined pipe.

Fig. 6. Effect of aeration gas flows on mass accumulation profiles during solids discharge from the inclined pipe with a 37 mm orifice size.

Fig. 7. Schematic view of critical differential pressures during solids discharge in the aerated standpipe and inclined pipe.

With the angle α in Fig. 7, the expression in Eq. (6) can be obtained,

$$s = \sin(\alpha)l = \sin(\alpha) \frac{m_t}{\rho_b A} \quad (6)$$

where s is the distance in vertical direction between the orifice exit P_2 and P_4 , as shown in Fig. 7.

The position of P_4 can therefore be determined. When $m_t = 4$ kg, the height s is calculated to be 16.6 cm. The distance between the aeration point P_3 and P_4 in the direction of solids flow is then calculated as around 15.4 cm.

ΔP_{34} between the aeration point P_3 and the observed turning point P_4 is calculated in Eq. (7).

$$\Delta P_{34} = \rho_s (1 - \varepsilon_{mf}) g (s - 0.044) \quad (7)$$

where ρ_s is the sand particle density, ε_{mf} is the void fraction at the minimum fluidization status, g is gravitational constant.

When the bed level is at the turning point P_4 , the pressure between P_3

and P_2 can be calculated in Eq. (8).

$$\Delta P_{32} = \Delta P_{34} \quad (8)$$

The pressure drop through the orifice is less than ΔP_{32} .

The sand mass flows using 54 mm and 75 mm orifices were also calculated via linearly fitting the mass accumulation profiles. The effect of orifice size on the sand mass flow rate is illustrated in Fig. 8(a). It is interesting to note that a good linearity between the solid mass flow and the orifice size can only be observed in the presence of a high flow of aeration gas in the inclined pipe. However, good linearity between the solid mass flow in the absence of aeration gas flow and the orifice cross section was obtained, as shown in Fig. 9. This indicates that in the absence of aeration gas flow, the solids discharge rate highly depends on the orifice opening area, while in tests with the aeration gas flow there could be other factors affecting the discharge rate.

The solids mass flow rate measured by the magnetic tracer-tracking method are compared to the results calculated by the mass accumulation method in the selected area (tests C#4 – C#6 as marked in Fig. 6). The comparison of accumulation and tracer-tracking results in the upper sensing zone is shown in Fig. 8(b). A good fit between the two methods can be observed for tests using a 37 mm orifice. However, the results from the two methods deviate from each other after increasing the orifice size to 54 mm and 75 mm. The significant change of the theta angle of the tracer in the upper sensing zone indicates that the tracer experienced a significant rotation, as marked in red circle area in Fig. 10, inferring a high tendency of a strong interaction between the tracer and sand particles at conditions with a high solids flow velocity. Moreover, as discussed and observed in Fig. 5(c) and (e), for tests C#8 to C#11, the tracer needs a short acceleration stage in the very beginning, inferring that there could be a discrepancy in motions between the tracer and sand particles especially in tests with a high sand discharge rate due to a large orifice and the presence of aeration gas flow.

The comparison of the result in the lower sensing zone shows an obvious discrepancy between the two methods for tests using a 37 mm orifice, while a good fit can be observed for tests using orifice sizes of 54 mm and 75 mm, as shown in Fig. 8(c), exhibiting a different trend in contrast to Fig. 8(b). The deviation of sand flows between the two methods in test C#6 in Fig. 8(c) could be attributed to the effect of a high aeration gas flow when using a narrow orifice, which can lead to the discrepancy in motions between the tracer and main solids flow.

However, the calculated results based on the tracer's travel time in the transition zone (Eq. (4)) fit well with the results obtained by the accumulation method for all tests conducted, as shown in Fig. 8(d). It seems that the disturbances that can arise from the initial discharge stage and the injection of the aeration gas can be avoided via adopting the new calculation method.

3.2.3. Prediction of solids discharge rate

The solid mass flow W_t can be described as the sum of the flow W_0 at basic conditions (gravity flow, no aeration gas) in the absence of aeration gas flow and the part W_a contributed by the aeration gas injection and other operating parameters (e.g., pressure gradient, which is neglected here but considered in Section 3.4).

$$W_t = W_0 + W_a \quad (9)$$

It can also be expressed as

$$W_t = \delta W_0 \quad (10)$$

where δ is a ratio factor, to indicate the effect of the presence of aeration gas and other operating parameters, e.g., pressure gradient over the bed. When $\delta < 1$, it means the discharge rate is less than that of gravity flow without aeration gas; while when $\delta > 1$, the solids discharge rate is larger than that of gravity flow, due to the contribution of aeration gas.

The Beverloo equation has been widely applied to estimate powder flows from a hopper when the top of a bin and the bottom of the hopper

Fig. 8. Effect of orifice size and aeration gas flow on solid discharge flow: (a) accumulation method, results from linear fitting of the mass accumulation profiles of tests C#4 – C#12; (b) results calculated by accumulation and magnetic tracer-tracking methods in the upper sensing zone; (c) results calculated by accumulation and tracer-tracking methods in the lower sensing zone; (d) results calculated by accumulation and tracer-tracking methods in the transition zone.

Fig. 9. Comparison of measured solid discharge flows and modeling predictions versus the cross-section area of orifice size at conditions without aeration gas flow.

are vented to atmosphere [56–58], as expressed as

$$W_{0,b} = C\rho_b\sqrt{g}(D_0 - kd_p)^{2.5} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 10. Effect of aeration flow on the change of tracer theta angles during discharge in the upper sensing zone.

where C was found to be close to 0.58, ρ_b is the bulk density of packed bed, D_0 is the orifice diameter, d_p is the size of sand particles, and k is a constant, about 1.6 for spherical sand particles [8].

Eq. (11) is only applicable to cylindrical bunkers and core flowing hoppers [58]. Since the effect of self-entrained gas generated in a gravity flow on the solids discharge rate is significant, therefore Eq. (11) needs to be revised by considering the pressure gradient generated by the entrained gas if the size of powder is less than 0.5 mm [59]. Eq. (12) is obtained.

$$W_{0,b} = C_{\rho_b} \sqrt{g + \left(\frac{dP}{dz}\right) \frac{1}{\rho_b} (D_0 - kd_p)}^{2.5} \quad (12)$$

Jones and Davidson [60] derived a correlation to describe the flow of solids discharged from a horizontal orifice at the side of a fluidized bed. Tallon and Davies [61] investigated solids discharge through an horizontal orifice from a fluidized bed, which also followed a similar equation.

$$W_{0,j} = C_D \frac{\pi D_o^2}{4} \sqrt{2\rho_s(1 - \varepsilon_{mf})\Delta P_o} \quad (13)$$

where C_D is orifice discharge coefficient, about 0.5, ΔP_o is orifice pressure drop, and ε_{mf} is minimum fluidization voidage in a fluidized bed.

However, Eq. (13) is for horizontal flow at the orifice and the gravity force was not included. For solids discharge without aeration in this study, the flow is driven by gravity force. Therefore, via replacing ΔP_o , Eq. (14) can be obtained for gravity flow

$$W_{0,g} = C_D \frac{\pi D_o^2}{4} \sqrt{2\rho_s(1 - \varepsilon_{mf})C_c\sqrt{g}} \quad (14)$$

where C_c is a constant, 10.25, as determined by linear fitting of experimental results obtained from tests in the standpipe and inclined pipe.

With the learning above, we propose Eq. (15)

$$W_{0,n} = C_D \rho_s (1 - \varepsilon) \sqrt{g} D_o^2 / 4 \quad (15)$$

For flows in a inclined pipe, a factor $f_{angle} = \frac{\sin(\alpha) + \cos\beta}{1 + \cos\beta}$ to include the effect of inclined pipe angle was added [62].

$$W_0 = \frac{C_D \rho_s (1 - \varepsilon) \sqrt{g} D_o^2}{4} f_{angle} = \frac{C_D \rho_s (1 - \varepsilon) \sqrt{g} D_o^2}{4} \frac{\sin(\alpha) + \cos\beta}{1 + \cos\beta} \quad (16)$$

where α is the angle of the inclined pipe to the horizontal, β is the internal kinetic angle of repose [63]. An angle of 35° was used for dry silica sand powders in this study [64].

The solids discharge rates estimated using Eq. (11), Eq. (14) and Eq. (16) are presented and compared with experimental results in Fig. 9. It can be observed that the calculation results from the Beverloo equation (Eq. (11)) deviate significantly from the experimental results when the orifice size is over 37 mm. Considering that an inclined pipe was used in this study compared to the work where the Beverloo equation was derived, an angle factor was added via $W_{0,b} \times f_{angle}$. However, the discrepancy between the calculation and experimental results is still obvious, which could be attributed to the high value of the power factor (2.5) used in the Beverloo equation. While with a lower power factor of 2 in Eq. (14), lower than that in the Beverloo equation, the corresponding calculation results of Eq. (14) fit well with the experimental results. It infers a highly dependent relationship between the solids discharge rate and the orifice cross-section area. It is therefore suitable to use a power factor of 2 in Eq. (16). A good fitting between the calculation results obtained from Eq. (16) and the experimental results was obtained. Eq. (16) was therefore adopted in the following model construction.

To include the effect of aeration gas flow, Shioji and Tokami [8] proposed a correlation, which includes the effect of pressure distribution of the particle flow, and can be expressed as

$$W_t = W_{0,b} \left[1 + K' \left(\frac{\Delta P_o}{\rho_b g D_o} \right)^{0.5} \right] \quad (17)$$

where $W_{0,b}$ is the mass flow estimated by the Beverloo correlation in Eq. (11), K' is a constant, ΔP_o is the pressure over the orifice. To present the effect of aeration gas flow on the solids flow, we included the aeration gas volume flow Q_0 in Eq. (18) and used the same power factor 0.5. The factor δ can be described using the following correlation.

$$\delta = \frac{W_0 + W_a}{W_0} = c + k Q_0^{0.5} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 11(a) shows the values of k and c obtained at conditions with three different orifice sizes. The value of c for the three lines is approximately 1, which is reasonable since the value of δ should be 1 in the absence of aeration gas flow.

With the three values of k obtained in Fig. 11(a), a correlation to show the dependence of k on the reciprocal of orifice diameter D_o can be formulated, as follows.

$$k = C_e (1/D_o) + C_f \quad (19)$$

where C_e and C_f are constant, obtained from linear fitting of the values of k in Fig. 11(b), with the values of 0.0197 and -0.0911 , respectively.

Combining Eq. (10), (11), (12) and (13), the solid mass flow can be described as

$$W_t = W_0 \left(\left(C_e \frac{1}{D_o} + C_f \right) Q_0^{0.5} + 1 \right) \quad (20)$$

It is found that δ is a function of $Q_0^{0.5}$ and $1/D_o$ in Eq. (20). δ was further directly correlated with $\frac{U_g^{0.5}}{D_o}$ and a good relationship was obtained as seen in Fig. 11(c).

Therefore, the model could be obtained in Eq. (21).

$$W_t = \frac{C_D \rho_s (1 - \varepsilon) \sqrt{g} D_o^2}{4} \frac{\sin(\alpha) + \cos\beta}{1 + \cos\beta} \left(k_0 \frac{U_g^{0.5}}{D_o} + 1 \right) \quad (21)$$

where k_0 is a constant, 0.1016, obtained in Fig. 11(c).

The constructed model was validated using experimental data and then used to predict the mass flow at various conditions, as shown in Fig. 11(d).

3.3. Determination of gas flow patterns in the aerated standpipe

Since most of the aeration gas injected escaped from the exit of the inclined pipe in the discharge tests in Fig. 5, there was no obvious bubbling phenomenon observed in the upper zone of the inclined pipe and the vertical standpipe. In other words, the aeration gas flows downward during discharge tests. However, in a standpipe connected to a fluidized bed riser, due to a higher pressure in the fluidized bed riser as compared to that over the standpipe top, the fluidization gas might escape from the riser up through the inclined pipe and standpipe. The injected aeration gas might also flow upward to the low-pressure side above the bed in the standpipe. The gas-solid flow pattern in the bed in the standpipe can change from the moving packed-bed status to bubbling fluidization, and even slug flow status in the presence of a high gas flow and a small standpipe size. In typical fluidized bed systems, e.g., gasifier and combustion boiler, the standpipe size is much smaller than that of the fluidized bed riser, with a high tendency of forming a slug flow during unstable operating conditions. Therefore, tests with a tracer in the standpipe with a controlled rising gas flow were also conducted to determine the gas flow patterns in the aerated standpipe.

3.3.1. Bubbling and slugging determination

Two tracers with different particle sizes and densities were used for fluidization tests, with the results of tracers' position profiles in x , y , and z directions and the corresponding rotation presented in Fig. 12. A significant waving motion can be observed from the position profile in z direction in Fig. 12(a), where the tracer with a diameter of 8 mm was used. The 8 mm tracer has an effective particle density of around 1000

Fig. 11. Model construction for predicting solid discharge flow in the aerated standpipe with different orifice sizes: (a) relationship between the ratio factor δ and the aeration gas flow $Q_0^{0.5}$; (c) relationship between the reciprocal of the orifice diameter $1/D_o$ and the slope rate obtained in Fig. 11(a); (c) relationship between the ratio factor δ and $U_g^{0.5}/D_o$; (d) predicted results of solid discharge flow using the constructed model.

kg/m^3 that is lower than the solids bulk density of 1610 kg/m^3 . The observed waving motion of the tracer position in z direction (direction along the length of the standpipe) in Fig. 12(a) indicates that the light tracer followed the rising bubble up and fell back to the bed surface quickly once bubbles ruptured. This can be confirmed by the relatively steep slope of the right-side curve of each peak in z direction in Fig. 12(a). Moreover, the sudden change of the tracer angles (theta and phi) in Fig. 12(b) also indicates that the tracer experienced frequent rotation during the waving in z direction. However, when using a 3 mm cylindrical tracer, indications of the waving phenomenon cannot be observed from the tracer position curves in Fig. 12(c) and the tracer rotation status in Fig. 12(d), indicating the importance of selecting a suitable tracer for determining and monitoring the gas-flow patterns in the aerated standpipe.

3.3.2. Measurement and calculation of slug and bubble properties

Considering the low density of the used tracer particle (8 mm) and the significant waving phenomenon observed in Fig. 12(a), it is reasonable to assume that the determined tracer movement, to some extent, can unveil the bubbling and slugging behaviors in the standpipe with aerated rising-up gas flow. As shown in Fig. 13(a), a peak was picked out from the position curve in z direction in Fig. 12(a), as marked in a red ellipse. The curves can be divided into four stages. Initially, at stage A, the tracer floated on the bed surface, as shown in Fig. 14(a). The tracer then moved up with the sand when a rising slugging bubble started poking through the wake above at stage B in Fig. 14(b). The

moving-up velocity of the tracer might increase since the rising bubble could carry up the tracer and particles further to the area over the bed after poking through the bed surface (stage C), as shown in Fig. 14(c). It should be noted that stage C can only be observed occasionally, which highly depends on whether the tracer was carried up to the splashing zone or not. Once the bubble ruptured, the tracer fell back to the bed surface (stage D) in Fig. 14(d). Then, the whole process would be repeated with the next slug. The velocities at stage B and C were calculated and the probability density function of the rising velocities is presented in Fig. 13(b). The velocity of around 2–3 cm/s has the highest probability density, which represents the movement at stage B. A high velocity of up to 8–12 cm/s can also be observed, which is mainly contributed by the carry-up process caused by slug bubbles at stage C. However, the high velocity at stage C in Fig. 13(a) is still much lower than the rising velocity of slug bubbles in the bed. The absolute slug velocity U_{SA} can be calculated using the Eq. (22) below [65],

$$U_{SA} = (U - U_{mf}) + 0.35\sqrt{gD_s} \quad (22)$$

where D_s is the standpipe diameter, U is the superficial gas velocity, U_{mf} is the minimum velocity of the sand particles, as calculated by Wen and Yu correlation [66].

Since the travel times of the tracer at different stages in Fig. 13(a) can be determined, the length of the slug bubble can be estimated via Eq. (23).

Fig. 12. Movement of tracers with different particle densities in the presence of aeration gas flow: (a) tracer waving motion in z direction due to rising and ruptured slugging bubbles, 8 mm tracer, with the zone for slugging frequency calculation marked; (b) change of tracer angles when following bubbles in Fig. 12(a), 8 mm tracer; (c) tracer moving in z direction in the emulsion phase, 3 mm tracer; (d) change of tracer angles in the emulsion phase in Fig. 12(c), 3 mm tracer.

$$L_s = (t_B + t_C)U_{sA} \quad (23)$$

The frequency of slug bubbles can also be calculated based on the waving behaviors detected by the tracer, with the calculation area marked in Fig. 12(a). The correlation to show the frequency as a function of the gas velocity and slug length is also available in the literature [65], which is expressed as.

$$f_s = \frac{U - U_{mf}}{L_s} = \frac{0.35\sqrt{g}}{N_T\sqrt{D_s}} \quad (24)$$

where N_T is a coefficient for the slug wake [67], and L_w/D_s can therefore be calculated.

The measured slugging behaviors in C#13 are shown in Table 3. The rising velocity of slug bubbles is around 86.7 cm/s, with a slugging frequency of 0.85 Hz. The lengths of the slug and wake, as shown in Fig. 14(d), were calculated to be 45 cm and 33 cm, respectively.

3.4. Solids discharge in the standpipe of a full-loop system

The standpipe, together with the inclined pipe, is always connected to the riser base to return solids to the fluidized bed, as shown in Fig. 15. The fluidization gas, injected via a distributor at the bottom of the riser, flows through the whole riser and carries up sand particles to the cyclone, where the solids are collected and recycled back to the riser base. The gas could also bypass through the inclined pipe, where the gas-solids flow pattern highly depends on the gas flow, size of the inclined

pipe, bed height in the standpipe, particle size, and the differential pressure between the riser base and the standpipe top. The factors can be intertwined together and affect each other. For example, the amount of bypassing gas can change with the bed height and the bed fluidization status in the standpipe; however, the bed fluidization status also highly depends on the gas velocity through the bed. After reaching a dynamic balance, these factors could remain relatively constant. A mathematical model can therefore be constructed for solids discharge in the standpipe of a full-loop fluidized bed system.

As shown in Fig. 15, assuming bed levels in the riser and standpipe reach stable condition, the pressure at P_2 is higher than P_1 , therefore there is a pressure gradient over the bed in the standpipe.

The Kozeny-Carman's equation could be used to describe the pressure drop for the laminar flow in a stable moving bed flow within the standpipe, as defined in Eq. (25) [68],

$$\frac{\Delta P}{z} = 180 \frac{(1 - \varepsilon)^2}{\varepsilon^3} \frac{\mu_f U_r}{d_s^2} \quad (25)$$

where $U_r = U_g - \varepsilon U_s$, is the superficial gas relative velocity, U_g is the superficial gas velocity through the standpipe, U_s is the downward velocity of solid particles through the standpipe, ε is the void fraction within the moving bed, μ_f is the fluid dynamic viscosity.

For gravity flow in the standpipe and inclined pipe without aeration gas, the solids discharged from the orifice is collected and separated, as shown in Fig. 7, the pressure at P_1 and P_2 are ambient pressure, $\Delta P_{21} = P_2 - P_1 = 0$. Thus, the pressure gradient $\frac{\Delta P}{z}$ over the bed is zero, the

Fig. 13. Tracer moving velocity when following rising bubble: (a) a typical profile in z direction divided into four stages; (b) probability density function of tracer rising velocity, with the two characteristics zones marked in the circle and rectangle areas for stage B and stage C, respectively.

Fig. 14. Schematic diagram to show the tracer movement at different stages in Fig. 13(a): (a) stage A; (b) stage B; (c) stage C; (d) stage D.

superficial gas velocity through the standpipe during a gravity flow is.

$$U_{g,0} = \epsilon U_{s,0} \quad (26)$$

which means the gas trapped in bed voids is carried down with the solids flow. $U_{s,0}$ is the solid downward velocity when P_1 and P_2 are at ambient

Table 3
Properties of measured and calculated slugging behaviors in C#13.

	Results	Notes
Minimum fluidization velocity, cm/s	10.2	Wen and Yu correlation [66]
Velocity of slug bubbles, cm/s	86.7	Eq. (22) [65]
Frequency of slug bubbles, Hz	0.85	Tracer measurement
Slug length of slugging bubbles, L_S , cm	45	Tracer measurement & Eq. (23)
Coefficient for slug wake, N_T	2.66	Tracer measurement & Eq. (24)
Length of slug wake L_w , cm	33	N_T

pressure and there is no aeration gas injection.

When a pressure difference ($P_2 > P_1$) was exerted on the bed, as a standpipe connected to the base of a fluidized bed riser in Fig. 15(a), $P_2 > P_1$, there is a pressure gradient ($\frac{\Delta P_{21}}{z_{21}}$) over the bed, as illustrated in Fig. 15(b). The superficial gas relative velocity leaking through the bed also changes according to Eq. (25). The superficial gas velocity can therefore be calculated by Eq. (27), after a derivation of Eq. (25).

$$U_g = \frac{1}{180} \frac{\Delta P_{21}}{z_{21}} \frac{\epsilon^3}{(1-\epsilon)^2} \frac{d_s^2}{\mu_f} + \epsilon U_s \quad (27)$$

Thus, compared to the gravity flow, the change of superficial gas velocity $U_g - U_{g,0} = U_g - \epsilon U_{s,0}$ can then be obtained and included in Eq. (21), as expressed in Eq. (28),

$$W_t = \frac{C \rho_s (1-\epsilon) \sqrt{g} D_0^2}{4} \frac{\sin(\alpha) + \cos\beta}{1 + \cos\beta} \left(k_0 \frac{(U_g - \epsilon U_{s,0})^{0.5}}{D_0} + 1 \right) \quad (28)$$

where the value of the constant k_0 is negative when there is a reverse gas flow (opposite to the solids flow direction in Fig. 7). It indicates a negative effect of the pressure difference ($P_2 > P_1$) on the solids discharge flow rate in the standpipe.

The solids downward velocity through the standpipe was then calculated in Eq. (29)

$$U_s = \frac{C \rho_s (1-\epsilon) \sqrt{g} D_0^2}{4} \frac{\sin(\alpha) + \cos\beta}{1 + \cos\beta} \left(k_0 \frac{(U_g - \epsilon U_{s,0})^{0.5}}{D_0} + 1 \right) / A \quad (29)$$

The calculation in Eq. (27) and Eq. (29) needs to be iterated until a convergence can be reached.

With the model and correlation above, the effect of the differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$ was then investigated, as shown in Fig. 16. Since a dense bed is preferred to maximize the solids discharge capacity and mitigate gas bypassing in the standpipe, it should be noted the calculation was conducted for the case when the bed in the standpipe is still in the moving packed-bed regime. For a certain bed height in the standpipe, the pressure difference $P_2 - P_1$ is kept below the level that can cause minimum fluidization in the bed of the standpipe and inclined pipe. It can be observed that, for all cases, the solids discharge rate decreases with the increase of $P_2 - P_1$ until $P_2 - P_1$ reaches a limit that causes bed minimum fluidization in the standpipe. For a bed height of 1 m in the standpipe with a 37 mm orifice, the discharge rate decreases from 0.74 to 0.16 kg/s prior to the occurrence of minimum fluidization, equivalent to a decrease of around 80%. While for orifices of 75 mm and 90 mm, the decrease could be lower to around 35% and 30%, respectively. The increase of the bed height in the standpipe can also significantly mitigate the decrease of discharge capacity when operating at the same differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$. For example, in cases using a 37 mm orifice with a differential pressure of 14 kPa, the decrease of discharge capacity can be lower to be 63% and 54% when increasing the bed height to 1.5 m and 2 m, respectively. Moreover, a low bed height also leads to a narrow process operating window. For example, at a low bed height of 1 m, the differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$ should be controlled below around 14 kPa. After increasing the bed height to 2 m, the allowable differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$ can increase to around 30 kPa.

Fig. 15. Operation of fluidized bed standpipe and inclined pipe: (a) schematic diagram of standpipe and inclined pipe connected to a fluidized bed riser; (b) differential pressure in the absence of aeration gas; (c) differential pressure in the presence of aeration gas.

Fig. 16. Effect of the differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$ on solids discharge rate W_t at conditions with various orifice sizes of 37 mm, 75 mm, and 90 mm, and different bed heights of 1 m, 1.5 m, and 2 m in the standpipe.

The role of aeration gas was also considered in the model. As shown in Fig. 15, the injected aeration gas could be split into two streams based on their flow directions, as expressed in Eq. (30).

$$Q_0 = Q_{up} + Q_{down} \quad (30)$$

Q_0 is the total volumetric flow of aeration gas injected (m^3/s), Q_{up} denotes the volumetric flow upward through the standpipe, and Q_{down} is the volumetric flow downward to the orifice exit. It is assumed that the aeration gas injection needs to balance the pressure P_2 , as shown in Fig. 15(c). Assuming $\Delta P_{31} = \Delta P_{21}$, the gas flow velocity above the injection point can be calculated.

$$U_g = \frac{1}{180} \frac{\Delta P_{21}}{z_{31}} \frac{\epsilon^3}{(1-\epsilon)^2} \frac{d_s^2}{\mu_f} + \epsilon U_s \quad (31)$$

The gas flow velocity downward can be calculated,

$$U_d = (Q_0 - Q_{up})/A = Q_0/A_i - (U_g - \epsilon U_{s,0}) \quad (32)$$

where A_i is the cross-sectional area of the inclined pipe.

Thus, the solid discharge rate can be calculated using Eq. (33).

$$W_t = \frac{C \rho_s (1-\epsilon) \sqrt{g} D_0^2 \sin(\alpha) + \cos \beta}{4} \frac{1 + \cos \beta}{1 + \cos \beta} \left(k_0 \frac{(U_d)^{0.5}}{D_0} + 1 \right) \quad (33)$$

where the value of the constant k_0 is negative when there is a reverse gas flow, U_d , meaning all gas flows upward through the bed; while the value of k_0 is positive when the gas flows downward in the same direction of solids moving-down velocity.

With the constructed model above, the effect of the aeration rate was investigated, as shown in Fig. 17. It can be observed that the injection of aeration gas flow can increase the solids discharge rate in the standpipe and counteract the adverse effect of the presence of a positive differential pressure $P_2 - P_1$ after increasing the aeration gas flow to a certain level, which highly depends on the differential pressure. In cases using a 37 mm orifice with a differential pressure of 1 kPa and a bed height of 1 m, an aeration gas flow of around $0.25 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$ is needed to reach the same solids discharge rate as that of the gravity flow ($P_2 - P_1 = 0$). When increasing the differential pressures to 5 and 12 kPa, the aeration gas flow needs to increase to 1.7 and $3.8 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$, respectively, to reach the same solids discharge rate as that of the gravity flow. A similar trend of the required aeration gas flow can also be observed from cases using a 75 mm orifice, as shown in Fig. 17.

4. Conclusion

Solids flow behaviors in an aerated fluidized bed standpipe have

Fig. 17. Effect of aeration gas flow on solids discharge rate W_t at conditions with various orifice sizes of 37 mm and 75 mm, and different differential pressures $P_2 - P_1$ of 1 kPa, 5 kPa, and 12 kPa in the standpipe with 1 m bed height.

been determined using the magnetic tracer-tracking method and investigated accordingly via constructing a model.

The tracer passing through the upper sensing zone in the vertical standpipe and a lower sensing zone in the inclined pipe were detected separately. In tests without injecting aeration gas, the sand mass flow obtained via measuring the tracer moving velocity in upper sensing zone fits well with the results from the mass accumulation method. The mass flows obtained in the lower sensing zone deviate from that obtained by the accumulation method, especially when using a 54 mm orifice, equivalent to an opening ratio of around 20 %. This indicates that the orifice might affect the tracer movement when approaching the narrow orifice, therefore resulting in lower measuring accuracy. The third analysis method that is based on the tracer's travel time in the transition zone between the two sensing zones has also been proposed and can measure the solids discharge accurately.

The injection of aeration gas significantly increases the solids discharge rate. The mass accumulation profiles show that a linear fitting is obtained until the mass accumulation reaches a turning point, after which the effect of aeration gas injection on the solids discharge vanishes. This could be explained by the change of aeration gas flow direction due to a low bed level. Discrepancies of the results between the magnetic tracer-tracking and mass accumulation methods can be observed both in the upper sensing zone, which is mainly caused by the tracer acceleration stage at the initial discharge stage, as well in the lower sensing zone, which could be attributed to the discrepancy in motions between the tracer and main solids flow in the presence of the aeration gas when using a narrow orifice. The sand mass flows based on the tracer's travel in the transition zone fit well with that from the accumulation method in all tests at conditions with different orifice sizes and aeration rates investigated in this study. It confirms that the magnetic tracer method can be used to predict the solid discharge rate in an aerated fluidized bed standpipe.

The bubbling and slugging behaviors after injecting a high amount of aeration gas were successfully determined when using a low-density tracer, providing insights into monitoring flow patterns, i.e., packed flow, bubbling, slugging, in the standpipe and measuring bubbles' properties. The tracer used in this study can be an efficient tool to determine the gas-solid flow pattern and behaviors in the standpipe.

The constructed model shows good accuracy in estimating the sand mass flow under gravity flow conditions with various orifice sizes and aeration gas flows. Moreover, the model was also further developed to

investigate the effect of pressure gradient over the bed and the aeration gas injection on the solids discharge rate in the standpipe in a full-loop fluidized bed system. A high differential pressure between the inclined pipe bottom exit and the vertical standpipe top can significantly decrease the solids discharge rate, while this can be mitigated by increasing the orifice size and the bed height in the standpipe. A much wider process window can be also obtained by increasing the bed height. Moreover, the adverse effect of the pressure gradient on the solids discharge rate in the standpipe can be effectively counteracted by injection aeration gas, the amount of which highly depends on the level of the differential pressure between the inclined pipe bottom exit and the vertical standpipe top.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Chunguang Zhou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christian Jonasson:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marcus Gullberg:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Investigation. **Fredrik Ahrentorp:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Christer Johansson:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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